
A Study on Socio-Economic Condition of BAIGA Tribal Community

Swathi K. 1*, **Vidya S. 2**** & Dr. Laveena D'Mello 3***

1* II MSW Srinivas University Pandeshwara, Mangalore Karnataka
swathisoordelu@gmail.com

2.** II MSW Srinivas University Pandeshwara, Mangalore Karnataka
vidyasoordelu@gmail.com

3***Assistant Professor, Social Work Department, Srinivas Institute of Management Studies,
Mangalore, Karnataka, India. E-mail : lavyoronha@gmail.com

Abstract

The tribe Baigas are found in the states of Madhya Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, Chhattisgarh and Jharkhand states of India with an approximate population of 2,50,000. But in Baiga-chuk in Mandla district and Balaghat district of Madhya Pradesh, Baigas are found in quite large numbers. Bijhwar, Narotia, Bharotiya, Nahar, RaiBhaina, and KadhBhaina are the sub-castes in the tribe. Many of this tribe people embraced Hinduism and their population came down due to this shifting of many people in this tribe. This tribe shows their link with the primitives of the Dravidian tribe who lived in the north-east India and later shifted to Jharkhand. The Baiga tribes prefer to go for shifting cultivation in the deep forest areas. They have the belief of not to plough the earth. It is mother earth, and if we plough it we are hurting our mother. And they do not want to hurt the mother earth, so they are against plough the earth. And if we repeat so, again and again they will commit the sin again to against the mother earth and put pressure on Mother earth to produce food from the same piece of land again, she will lose her fertility and become weakened. The food of this tribe is quite coarse and does not reflect any modern taste at all. An oral Interview Schedule method was designed to collect required data, since the majority of them are illiterate's interview schedule found to be more useful. Both Interview method and observation method have been used covering the various aspects of the study. Simple Random Sampling method has been used in this study

Keywords: Baiga tribes, primitive, Culture, occupation, and traditions.

INTRODUCTION

The Indian constitution assigns special status to the Scheduled tribes (STs). Traditionally referred to as advises, van basis, tribals, STs constitute about 8% of the Indian population. India Census figures for the ten-year period from 2001 to 11 showed the number of this tribe at 39, though this tribe had a population of 30,000 in 1911. There are 573 Scheduled tribes living in different parts of the country which are different from the mainstream people of the where they live. Baiga tribe is a primitive tribe found in central provinces of the country such as Madhya Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, Chhattisgarh and Jharkhand. The largest number of Baiga is found in Baiga-chuck in Mandia district Balaghat district of Madhya Pradesh. Baiga are connected to Indo-aryan Dravidian tribes who have unique socio-economic status and life style. The major part of Baiga earning is spent on food and clothing. In Baiga community, the family is small but the kinship structures are quite strong. They follow strict marriage rules such as incest is a taboo, no marriage with outsiders is permitted, and monogamy is the general rule. The Baiga have expertise in medicine and the priests have their special importance. Baigas lived in the forests and carry out shifting, slash and Burn cultivation for thousands of years without any influence or competition from other Indian residents. The second largest grouping of the Baigs lives in Bilaspur, Kabirdham and Surguja districts of Chhattisgarh.

PRACTICES OF BAIGA TRIBES

Shift Cultivation: The Baiga tribes practice shifting cultivation in the forest areas. They say they never ploughed the Earth, because it would be a sin to scratch the breast of their Mother, and they could never ask their Mother to produce food from the same Patch of earth time and time again-she would have become weakened. For this reason, Baigas used to live a semi nomadic life, practice Bear, or 'dahiya' cultivation-out of respect, not aggression. These techniques rather than being a cause of deforestation have been shown to be effective conservation devices, employed for centuries by tribal peoples. Woods men and hunters, the Baigas of Central India were reluctant to do work for others. They saw themselves as people of the forest, who could only live on the produce of the forest. It was below the dignity of a Baiga to become a laborer.

Tattooing: One of the tribes for whom tattooing is integral part of their lifestyle is the Baiga tribes. This Tribe inhabits the dense hilly forests in the eastern part of the Satpuras, in Shahdol, Bilaspur, Rajnandgaon, Mandla, and Balaghat districts. It is believed that this tribe is an offshoot of the Bhuiya tribe of Chhota Nagpur. A distinguishing feature of the Baiga tribe is that their women are famous for sporting tattoos of various kinds on almost all parts of their body.

Marriage and family: Premarital relation between men and women are common and socially sanctioned. Formal engagement takes place at any age, though frequently after

puberty. The engagement process was initiated by the male. The consent of his desired spouse and her parents (along with payment of the bride – price) are required before the betrothal may take place.

Kinship: The baigas are strictly endogamous, though Baiga men who take non-Baiga wives may have their spouses admitted to the tribe by the performance of certain rites. The tribe is divided in to several relatively endogamous jat. Each of this jet occupies a separate territory and there is considerable intergroup rivalry over the issue of superiority the income from the manufacture of bamboo products, from the cultivation and sale of honey, and by hiring themselves out as laborers.

Industrial Arts: The Baiga do not spin fibers or weave cloth. Clothing is purchased in local markets. Few implements are manufactured by Baiga artisans. Iron implements such as the axe (tangia), sickle (hassia), arrowheads, digging tools (kudari and sabar), wood plane (basula). The ceremony described above may be performed once in life. A less elaborate ceremony called the haldi – pani is churi – pairana marriage may be performed more than once. The latter ceremony is roughly equivalent to marriage in a registry office. The Baiga themselves Bhumiaraaja or are a Munda are Kolarian people located in the central highlands of India. The name Baiga means Sorcerer, medicine man and is applied in this sense to the priests of the Chota Nagapur Tribe.

Rituals: As India sought Independence from British rule mythological traditions about Mahatama Gandhi began to emerge, superhuman status being ascribed to him by the Baiga. Nevertheless, Gandhi`s attitude towards alcohol prohibition did result in some negative by Baiga sentiment. Villages are located in areas convenient for cultivation with consideration also being given to the aesthetic value and degree of isolation of the intended site. Village locations vary (Jungles, High hills, and valleys) but whenever possible, a location a top a steep hill, with limited access by foot path is preferred. Men and Women share the responsibility for cooking (the husband assuming full responsibility when the wife is menstruating), gathering water, fishing, and wood cutting. Only men are allowed to hunt, and women are not permitted to make khumris or thatch roofing for houses.

PROBLEMS THE BAIGA TRIBES

The main problems the Baiga tribal face are; They possess small and uneconomical landholdings because of which their crop yield is less and hence they remain chronically indebted. Only a small percentage of the population participates in occupational activities in the secondary and tertiary sectors. Tribal government programmes have not significantly helped the tribal`s in raising their economic status. The British policy had led to ruthless exploitation of the tribal`s in various ways as it favored the zamindars, landlords, moneylenders, forest contractors, and excise, revenue and police officials. About 45 per cent

of the tribal's are engaged in cultivation and most of them are landless and practice shifting cultivation. They need to be helped in adopting new methods of cultivation.

FINDINGS

The major findings in the case study are; They are Premarital relation between men and women are common and socially sanctioned in baiga community. Their socio-economic condition was very poor, because poverty, Illiteracy, Superstitious beliefs etc. They are depending upon shifting cultivation. They are traditionally follow tattooing as an art They are working together both men and women like Cooking, gathering water, Fishing and Woodcutting.They are do not spin fibers or weave cloth.They are migrating between one place to another.

CONCLUSION

The Baigas were one of several tribal people in the Central Provinces. In the first provincial census (1866), aboriginal and hill tribes formed one-fifth of the population of nine million. Gonds accounted for almost three-fourths of these tribal people, while the remainder included Baigas, Korkus, Bhils, Kols, and others. Most lived on the middle spine of the Satpura hills, with its plateaus and valleys, which divided the province between the northern, southern, and southeastern plains. Baigas, along with some of the Gonds, occupied the Maikal range of the eastern Satpura hills. The heavily forested and sparsely populated range gave rise to streams and rivers that flowed in all direction. The Narbudda and its tributaries flowed west; and tributaries of the Wainganga emerged to join that river as it flowed south into the Godavari. In these highlands were the boundaries of three administrative districts of the Central Provinces well as the boundary between the province and Rewa State. At times the area was referred to as Baigadesh, Baiga-country.

SUGGESTION

The major suggestions are: To provide agricultural benefits; To provide health and nutrition education;To provide training about government policy and programmes; To improve communication and transport facility for their betterment; To improve sanitation and reducing communicable disease; and to provide education for their improvement. If all these areas are given important some remarkable changes and progress can brought in the tribal community.

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